
A STUDY ON FINANCIAL LITERACY ON SAVING AND INVESTMENT HABITS AMONG YOUTH OF NAVI MUMBAI

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ABSTRACT

The youth of Navi Mumbai represent an important segment of the population who are beginning to make their own decisions about saving and investment money. However, many young individuals still lack sufficient knowledge about financial management and the various saving and investment options available in the market. Financial literacy plays a crucial role in helping individuals understand financial concepts such as savings, budgeting, banking services and investment opportunities allowing them to make financial decisions. Improving financial awareness among the youth of Navi Mumbai helps them in saving practices and making better decisions. Therefore, it is important to study financial literacy and examine its impact on the saving and investment habits of the youth of Navi Mumbai.

Keywords: *Financial Literacy, Saving Habits, Financial Awareness, Investment Decisions, Youth of Navi Mumbai*

INTRODUCTION

Research on financial literacy among the youth has become important over the years as young individuals have begun managing their own finances and making decisions related to savings and investments. It has become necessary for individuals to understand basic financial concepts in order to make decisions. Financial literacy is widely studied in fields like finance, economics and consumer studies as it helps individuals to develop knowledge and skills required for financial management.

Information and awareness play a vital role in shaping financial behavior. Young individuals who have a better understanding of financial matters are more likely to develop good saving habits and make smarter investment choices. Individuals who are aware financially contribute positively to the economy as they tend to plan their finances better.

The youth of Navi Mumbai represent an important group that is gradually becoming more financially independent. Given that they have begun managing their own finances they also started taking responsibility for their financial decisions.

Financial Literacy

Financial literacy defines the knowledge and understanding of financial concepts that help the individuals to make informed decisions about saving, budgeting, investing and managing money. It also helps individuals with the ability to examine financial products, plans for future financial needs and manage risks effectively.

Financial literacy also plays an important role in improving financial awareness of individuals and society as a whole. Financially well aware people are able to plan for their future, avoid unnecessary debts and make better decisions.

Definitions

According to Annamaria Lusardi and Olivia S. Mitchell (2014):

Financial literacy means the knowledge as well as the ability to understand basic financial concepts and use them to make effective financial decisions.

According to OECD (2013):

Financial literacy is the combination of knowledge, skills, awareness and behavior necessary to make decisions and achieve financial goals.

These concepts analyze how financial literacy influences the saving and investment habits of the youth of Navi Mumbai.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

- **Garg and Singh (2018)** analyzed the financial literacy level among youth in India and found that although young people have access to various financial products, their understanding of financial planning and investment instruments remains limited. The study suggested introducing financial education programs in academic institutions to improve financial decision-making.

- **Kumar and Mishra (2019)** examined the relationship between financial literacy and investment decisions among young professionals in urban India. Their findings indicated that financially literate individuals are more likely to invest in systematic investment plans (SIPs), stocks, and mutual funds compared to those with limited financial knowledge.
- **Gupta and Jain (2021)** investigated the impact of financial literacy on investment behavior among youth in metropolitan cities. The research concluded that financial knowledge positively influences risk tolerance and encourages youth to participate in capital markets and long-term investments.

RELEVANCE OF THE STUDY

Navi Mumbai is city which is rapidly expanding where almost everyone is online , it is a very ideal place to study this . Technical jobs , social media influencers, and small and simple investment opportunities are around the youth in this place. This study examines how the pressures like getting rich quickly posts or having access to almost every apps actually affect people's spending and saving habits.

Objectives of the study

- To analyze the saving and investment habits of the youth of Navi Mumbai influenced by financial literacy.
- To examine the level of awareness among the youth of Navi Mumbai regarding different saving and investment options.
- To determine whether the youth of Navi Mumbai plans and manage their savings before making investment decisions.

Scope of the study

This study is very clear about how it examines the financial literacy of the young people in Navi Mumbai and how it affects their investment and saving habits. By putting these limits. The study remains focused on what is really important to this certain group and area.

- Location - Only Navi Mumbai (Vashi , Belapur , Panvel and Kharghar)
- People - Young adults (18- 30 year old)
- Topics - it observes people's financial literacy, investing and saving strategies, risk tolerance and usage of digital banking apps.
- Testing - to examine how an individual's background affects their financial literacy.

METHODOLOGY

Class of respondent: For the purpose of the survey, a total 100 respondents from Navi Mumbai have been selected on a random basis.

Gender	No. of respondents
Male	36
Female	58
Other	6
Total	100

Sampling Method: For collection of Primary data non-probability convenience sampling method will be used.

Method of data collection:

1. **Primary data:** will be collected from 100 respondents from Navi Mumbai who have been selected on a random basis.
2. **Secondary data:** will be used to support the study collected from books, journals, websites, and newspapers.

Statistical Technique of analysis of data: Descriptive and Analytical technique.

Limitations of the study

1. The participants in the study are limited to navi mumbai only and they may not represent the perspective of the entire youth.
2. The study relies on self reported responses which may include bias or overestimation of financial knowledge

3. This study was conducted within a limited time frame which acted as constraint and does not capture dynamics in financial behaviour over a longer period of time
4. This study has Limited depth of financial evaluation as the financial literacy is a broad concept and questions asked may not fully represent advanced financial knowledge and complex decisions making abilities
5. The research mainly focuses on demographic variables such as age, gender, income, and education . However other factors that may influence financial behaviour such as psychological traits, family financial background, economic conditions were not examined in detail in the study.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

H₀: Financial literacy has no significant impact on the saving and investment habits of youth in Navi Mumbai.

H_a: Financial literacy does improve the saving and investment habits of youth in Navi Mumbai.

RESULT

● **Awareness of Financial Literacy**

1. I am aware about the basic financial concepts such as inflation, interest rates, and compounding.

Response	Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	56	56%
Agree	27	27%
Neutral	14	14%
Disagree	3	3%
Strongly Disagree	0	0%
Total	100	100%

The above table describes most of the respondents are aware of various financial instruments, supported by 83% agreeing or strongly agreeing. Only a small percentage are not aware about it. This reflects a good level of financial literacy among the youth of Navi Mumbai.

2. Do you regularly save a portion of your income/allowance?

Response	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	95	95%
No	5	5%
Total	100	100%

A large proportion of respondents (95%) regularly save a part of their income, indicating strong saving habits among youth in Navi Mumbai. Only a small percentage of respondents do not save regularly

3. Do you invest in any financial instruments?

Response	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	96	96%
No	4	4%
Total	100	100%

The above results show that 96% of respondents are investing in financial instruments, which denotes a very high level of participation among youth in Navi Mumbai. Only a small part of the respondents do not invest.

4. Impact of Financial Literacy

Financial literacy has helped me make better investment and financial decisions.

Response	Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	62	61.6%
Agree	18	17.2%
Neutral	17	16.2%
Disagree	3	3%
Strongly Disagree	2	2%
Total	100	100%

The major part of the respondents (78.8%) agree that financial literacy helps them take better decisions while investing. This shows a strong and positive impact of financial literacy on the youths' investment behaviour in Navi Mumbai.

5. Do you think financial literacy programs should be made compulsory for the youth?

Response	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	98	98%
No	2	2%
Total	100	100%

The major proportion of the respondents (98%) believes financial literacy programs should be compulsory for youth, because it signifies a high demand for structured financial education among young individuals in Navi Mumbai.

CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

The study signifies the rapidly increasing importance of financial literacy among youth in Navi Mumbai and how it influences their investment and saving habits. The findings denote that a large part of the young individuals have basic financial awareness, and they actively engage themselves in saving and investment activities. But gaps still exist in practically applying the financial knowledge and informed decision making regarding investments.

The study confirms that financial literacy does play a significant role in shaping an individual's financial behaviour and promotes long-term stability among youth.

Strengthening financial education through structured programs that are supported by relevant and updated facilities can further empower youth to make better financial decisions and build a secure financial future

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